

**Mila A. Reforma
(1943-2023)**

Mila A. Reforma, 79, retired professor of public administration and former college secretary at the National College of Public Administration and Governance, University of the Philippines (UP-NCPAG), passed away on 27 July 2023.

Professor Reforma's humble yet invaluable dedication to teaching, research, and extension in public administration spanned more than four decades. Professor Reforma received her master's degree in public administration in 1970 from the then College of Public Administration (CPA), University of the Philippines Diliman. She also studied for a special course on public policy at the Kennedy School of Government, Harvard University. In 1974, Professor Reforma, known to her students and colleagues as Ma'am Mie, joined the faculty of CPA. Around the same period, she also began her stint as an academic administrator, serving as assistant to the college secretary. She later served as college secretary and director of the Center for Public Administration and Governance Education (CPAGE), a post she held for several years. After retiring in 2008, Professor Reforma continued to teach as a professorial lecturer for graduate students of UP-NCPAG until 2011.

Professor Reforma was a well-published scholar. A renowned teacher on quantitative research methods, she led by example, having conducted various local studies on rural health and poverty alleviation programs, and urban housing policies in informal communities. She contributed seven articles tackling these areas for the *Philippine Journal of Public Administration (PJPA)* from 1977 to 1981. She later became an editorial board member of the journal from 1978 to 1982, and an issue editor for the 1981 and 1994 volumes of the *PJPA*.

Professor Reforma was also author, co-author, and editor of several books on administrative reform, decentralization, and local governance in the Asia-Pacific region, most of which were in collaboration with the late Raul P. de Guzman. She also published in other academic and professional journals.

Professor Reforma had a global outlook in public administration research and education, which might be attributed to her active engagement with several international organizations. As a long-time director of research and publications of the Eastern Regional Organization for Public Administration (EROPA), she served as editor of the organization's newsletter, *EROPA Bulletin*, and as the first editor-in-chief of its flagship academic journal, *Asian Review of Public Administration (ARPA)*. She also edited proceedings of the organization's annual conferences. Even after her retirement, she continued to provide outstanding editorial support to the ARPA journal.

Moreover, Professor Reforma was consultant to various government and international organizations, such as the UNICEF, UNDP, NEDA, the Office of the Vice President, among others. In various capacities, Professor Reforma closely worked with these agencies in their international projects on decentralization and bureaucracy.

The *PJPA* fondly remembers and celebrates Ma'am Mie's passion for public administration research and education, and her tireless dedication and effectiveness as a teacher.